

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DISCOURSE AS A BRANCH OF LINGUISTICS

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Abstract

Linguistics studies the whole factors of the languages. Language is the best communication tool for keeping the relations between the peoples and nations, for developing political, educational, scientific and economical system all over the world. For that reason, it is one of the hardest loads for scholarships to analyze theory of languages and present the essential suggestions to the new generation. Furthermore, as the discourse arises the key of the effective communication, we, scientists should research and prove the field in details.

Keywords: linguistics, communication, discourse, discourse analysis, speech, text.

Introduction

Discourse branch of linguistics is the study of language of sentences; the analysis of features of language that extend beyond the limits of a sentence. A scholar suggests that the term discourse analysis is very ambiguous. According to them, Discourse Analysis “refer mainly to the linguistic analysis of naturally occurring connected speech or written discourse.” Explaining further, discourse analysis “refers to attempts to study the organisation of language above the sentence or above the clause, and therefore to study larger linguistic units, such as conversational exchanges or written texts.”

Main body

Discourse Analysis takes linguistic enquiry beyond the clause-bound ‘objects’ of grammar and semantics to the level of analysing ‘utterances’, ‘texts’ and ‘speech events’. It engages itself with meaning that cannot be located in the ‘linguistic system’. Discourse Analysis deals with language use in social contexts; and in particular with interaction or dialogue between speakers.

Deborah Tannen, in explaining Discourse analysis, defines it as “the analysis of language ‘beyond the sentence’. She submits that this analysis contrasts with the typical analysis by modern linguistics which mainly deals with the study of grammar: the study of smaller bits of language, such as sounds (phonetics and phonology), parts of words (morphology), meaning (semantics), and the order of words in sentences (syntax). According to her, “Discourse analysts study larger chunks of language as they flow together.” Discourse analysts examine larger discourse context so that they can determine how it affects the meaning of a sentence. For instance, let us look at the example of two signs/sentences at a swimming pool given by Charles Fillmore:

Please use the toilet, not the pool.

Pool for members only.

If these two sentences are read separately, they might seem reasonable; but when we take them together as a single discourse, we will have to check again the interpretation of the first sentence having read the second sentence. This is what discourse analysts do. Rechecking the first sentence to properly determine its meaning is known in Discourse Analysis as Reframing. How is Discourse Analysis studied? The first thing to say about methods for studying discourse, is that Dis-

course Analysis is not itself a research method, but rather a field that uses other branches of linguistics to look at the ways in which communication takes place between people in varying contexts and with varying motives. Here are a couple of areas a discourse analyst might look at.

Conversation Analysis. The study of social interaction. This can encompass both verbal language and non-verbal language such as body language.

Interactional Sociolinguistics. A subdiscipline of sociolinguistics that takes interaction into account when studying the meaning created by language users. Pragmatics Considers how meaning is constructed beyond the literal meaning of an utterance as well as focusing on implied meanings.

These areas would be of particular interest to someone who is studying face to face interactions or the way in which films and TV portray people. For example, a researcher may use some of these disciplines to look at the way the TV shows such as 'Friends' portray everyday life. They would then ask if these portrayals are accurate and what effect, if any, they have on people's perceptions and attitudes.

Critical Discourse Analysis. There is also a sub-branch of Discourse Analysis, called Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), which takes a more politically motivated standpoint. Researchers in this field use all the same methods open to 'traditional' DA, but use them to investigate and challenge the way in which ideologies are encouraged. If we look again at the 'freedom fighter vs terrorist' issue, someone from a CDA perspective will actively look at how people are being portrayed when they are referred to as one of these things. They will look at the motivations present and investigate what outcomes could come from painting a certain set of people as 'terrorists'. They will then use this information as a base for challenging established views.

Conclusion

In the result of research of discourse and discourse analysis, we are able to conclude it like the following. Discourse analysis draw breath as the analysis of language beyond the sentence. It is an effective way to communicate in written and oral forms where communication takes place between people in different contexts and with various conditions. Moreover, there are sets of subbranches, like conversation analysis, interactional sociolinguistics, critical discourse analysis, that

